

A Conjecture on the Distribution of Prime Gaps

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Abstract

Let $\mathbb{P} = \{p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots\}$ be the sequence of primes in increasing order and $g_n = p_{n+1} - p_n$ the gap between consecutive primes. This paper proposes the Main Proposition and the Weak Proposition, characterizing lower bounds on the distribution density of any even gap in sufficiently large intervals.

Keywords: prime number distribution; consecutive prime gaps; prime pair conjecture; gap density

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1 Main Proposition

Main Proposition

For any even integer $c \geq 2$ and any positive integer k , there exists a threshold $N_k(c) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\forall N \geq N_k(c), \quad \#\{n : p_n \in [N + 1, c(N - 1)], g_n = c\} \geq k.$$

2 Weak Proposition

Weak Proposition

For any even integer $c \geq 2$ and any positive integer k , there exists a threshold $N_k(c) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\forall N \geq N_k(c), \quad \#\{p \in [N + 1, c(N - 1)] : p \in \mathbb{P}, p + c \in \mathbb{P}\} \geq k.$$